

Online Educational Resources Library

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Neumohealth and
environment

TITLE	LINK	TYPE OF RESOURCE	AUTORSHIP	LICENCE	LANGUAGE	TITLE
How to use a pulse oximeter in children	https://bit.ly/3Qf9juW	Interactive resource	created by others	Copyright	English	How to use a pulse oximeter in children
How Do Your Lungs Work?Lung Foundation Australia	https://rb.gy/3nbp0	Video	created by others	Copyright	English	How Do Your Lungs Work?Lung Foundation Australia
Neumohealth educational guide presentation	https://organkitsproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Digital-Educational-Guide-NEUMOHEALTH-V2.pdf	Visual presentation	Self-authorship	Other	Turkish	Neumohealth educational guide presentation
Παρουσίαση Neumohealth & Environment	https://view.genially.com/671604d930121d32be9c00e9/presentation-gre-neumohealth-and-environment	Interactive resource	Self-authorship	Other	Greek	Παρουσίαση Neumohealth & Environment
Presentazione Neumohealth & Environment	https://view.genially.com/671604dc30121d32be9c038b/presentation-ita-neumohealth-and-environment	Interactive resource	Self-authorship	Other	Italian	Presentazione Neumohealth & Environment
Presentación de Neumohealth and environment	https://view.genially.com/671604a36989ca89dd88fa6b/presentation-esp-neumohealth-and-environment	Interactive resource	Self-authorship	Other	Spanish	Presentación de Neumohealth and environment

Neumohealth ve çevre sunumları	https://view.genially.com/671604df97695fe3ccfb1422/presentation-tur-neumohealth-and-environment	Interactive resource	Self-authorship	Other	Turkish	Neumohealth ve çevre sunumları
make a lung model	https://www.sciencebuddies.org/stem-activities/lung-model	video	created by others	Copyright	English	make a lung model
make a lung model	https://youtu.be/XmWkgZ88w_Y?si=qawxrCr3ughG6h1u	Video	created by others	Other	Turkish	make a lung model
Make a sick lung model	https://youtu.be/nAcglaesrgA?si=v5ZQXcCa1jc0-WYk	Video	created by others	Other	English	Make a sick lung model
How Smoking Just 1 CIGARETTE Affects Your Lungs	https://youtu.be/YS02MCx9f2c?si=3bnVThfv51iU8PBn	Video	created by others	Other	English	How Smoking Just 1 CIGARETTE Affects Your Lungs
Healthy Lung test	https://www.youtube.com/shorts/kw9y4cGbnWQ	Video	created by others	Other	English	Healthy Lung test
Healthy Lung Unhealthy Lung	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=69R0E_Rg_mQ	Video	created by others	Other	English	Healthy Lung Unhealthy Lung
Models, Structure & Function: 'Syringe Model' of breathing	https://youtu.be/Qb3gjrQUU1w?si=MzjEQQp0zEfiHgAX	Video	created by others	Other	English	Models, Structure & Function: 'Syringe Model' of breathing
Akciğer Sesleri (Ral,Ronküs,Plevral Frotman,Wheezing,Stridor)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TaLbvs2M_o8	Video	created by others	Other	Turkish	Akciğer Sesleri (Ral,Ronküs ,Plevral Frotman,Wheezing,Stridor)

Pulse oximeter - use for children	https://healthify.nz/health-a-z/p/pulse-oximeter-children/	Visual presentation	created by others	Copyright	English	Pulse oximeter - use for children
How to measure someone's oxygen levels	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pyjbd_kayA	Video	created by others	Other	english	How to measure someone's oxygen levels
Easy fractal drawing	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dfvSulD311Y	video	created by others	other	English	Easy fractal drawing
What is a fractal?	https://iternal.us/what-is-a-fractal/	Visual presentation	created by others	Other	English	What is a fractal?
What is Turkish marble art ?	https://aregem.ktb.gov.tr/?_Dil=1	Visual presentation	created by others	Copyright	Turkish	What is Turkish marble art ?
Environmental Concept Art & Design.	https://www.adobe.com/uk/creativecloud/illustration/discover/environmental-concept-art.html	Visual presentation	created by others	Copyright	English	Environmental Concept Art & Design.

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